

Employee Empowerment and Organizational Performance a Study of Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri

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Abstract:- Employees, no doubt, are the prime element in every organization, whether profit or non-profit making organizations. They come into the organization with potentials and capabilities that must be tapped and harnessed by the management under the human resources management unit. To effectively and efficiently utilize these raw talents and for better and improved performance management support is required, in form of empowerment. Hence, this paper is aimed at examining the effects of employee training, delegation of authority and work environment on their performance, commitment and satisfaction on their jobs. As a descriptive research a sample size of 190 teaching and non-teaching staff members were selected randomly. A structured questionnaire with Likert's 5-point measurement scale was administered. The data were analyzed using correlation coefficient and regression model. The results of the analysis showed that employee empowerment through training, authority delegation and work environment have positive effects on the employees' performance, which must be sustained by the organization.

Keywords:- Empowerment, Training, Work environment, Delegation of authority and performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employees are the core elements of every organization, and for them to strive to achieve the organizational goals there is need to recognize them. Their impact on organization performance is significant as their roles boost the firms' competitiveness, image and also enhance customer loyalty. Kumar and Kumar(2017)in 21st century the industrial organizations are more concerned about knowledge workers because they are the real drivers of business. Consequently, these workers or employees must be given the necessary emotional and intellectual support, freedom, power and authority to perform to satisfactory level for organizational benefits. This underscores the importance of empowerment.

When employees are empowered, their confidence degree and self-reliance will increase. This extra confidence is a good thing because it creates job satisfaction and high levels of productivity. However, in some cases, confidence levels can be taken too far and end up crossing the line into arrogance. Arrogant employees are difficult to deal with, do not take directives well and can become insubordinate. Working in this type of work environment takes its toll on

employees and they once again become dissatisfied with their job and productivity levels decrease (Kumar & Kumar, 2017).

Employee empowerment is about making the employee independent in terms decision making by the management while providing the necessary strategies, means and resources to do so. According to Rajesh (2015) employee empowerment is giving employees a certain degree of autonomy and responsibility for decision-making regarding their specific organizational tasks. He further opined that it allows decisions to be made at the lower levels of an organization where employees have a unique view of the issues and problems facing the organization at a certain level.

The concept of employee empowerment is a trending concept that has been embraced by mostly industrial organizations. Hence, many organizations have initiated and established different empowerment strategies and approaches with the aim of boosting the productivity of the employees. Such techniques included training programmes, delegation, decentralization, and running a flat organizational structure in the organization. In Rajesh (2015) this approach may be used to improve performance, productivity, service quality, satisfaction of employees and customers and increasing organizational efficiency while in Richa, Surat. & Amrinder (2016) motivated and empowered employees have the capability which can help the organizations to reach at top. They further opine that a good manager can use empowerment techniques to enhance the quality and quantity of performance of employees.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Employees are seen as the core elements of every organization, and for them to strive to achieve the organizational goals there is need to recognize them. They seem to have low organizational commitment, with absence of job satisfaction and low productivity. This is as a result of the fact that the organization does not give them the necessary and maximum freedom to make decisions relating to their areas of jurisdictions. Again, the management as discovered does adopt both centralization of authority on strategic issues and decentralization over other matters, but not adequately implemented thereby reducing the contributions and inputs of the employees in terms of their suggestions and ideas. The work environment as also observed has not holistically encouraged employees to perform maximally. The performance of the employees has

not been optimal due to certain policies from the management.

A. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To determine the impact of training on employees' performance.
- To analyze the effect of delegation of authority on employees' satisfaction.
- To discover the effect of work environment on employee commitment.

B. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What is the impact of training on employees' performance?
- What is the effect of delegation of authority on employees' job satisfaction?
- What is the effect of work environment on employees' commitment?

C. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- Ho1: Training does not have any effect on employees' performance
- Ho2: Delegation of authority does not encourage employee job satisfaction
- Ho3: Work environment does not affect employees' commitment.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Employee empowerment is a concept that has attracted several researches. According to Siegall & Gardner (2000) in Alejandro & Yolanda (2014) the concept of empowerment is closely aligned with this thrust to gain organizational effectiveness through the wise utilization of human resources. Kumar & Kumar (2017) opined that empowerment has been defined in numerous ways, but most authors agree that the core element of empowerment involves giving employees a discretion (or latitude) over certain task related activities. Quinn & Gretchen (1997) in Abdulkadir (2016) states that empowerment of human resources is usually used in the same meaning with authorizing and assigning responsibility, in other words, as empowering and transfer of authority. It should be noted that this understanding has some deficiencies. It is a need for human resources to empower. However, empowerment has to have some more aspects such as motivation and taking part in. Employee Empowerment starts from high level managers; and continues with the understanding of vision, mission and values of the organization and the applications which enables the employees to feel them responsible, free, and competent for the organization. Employee empowerment is also a period which consists of taking risks, development and change.

Klagge (1998) sees empowerment as to release improved "power and authority" along with the relevant duties and expertise to employees. It is seen as a powerful management tool, which is used to exchange the shared vision that the organization expects to materialize into common goals. The reality is that empowerment could be utilized as an expression to explain diverse plans providing

an expedient oratory, advocating that empowerment is hypothetically a fine object that fabricates a, win-win" condition for workers and administrators (Raquib, 2010). Employee Empowerment in work setting means giving employees the means, ability, and authority to do something. It involves efforts to take full advantage of organization's human resources by giving everyone more information and control over how they perform their jobs. Various techniques of empowerment range from participation in decision-making to the use of self-managed or empowered teams.

Sambal, Sihle & Charles (2018) opine that employee empowerment fosters a spirit of team work within the organization and uplifts the image of the organization. Hill (1991) in Sambal et al (2018) states that team work offers an opportunity of building a relationship between management and employees, a decline in resistance to change due to sectional interest and less organizational rigidity. Employees who realize the support, empowerment, opportunities and recognition provided by the organization will dedicate their effort, time and energy to service customers and to achieve the objectives of the organization. Therefore, employee performance depends on the organizational support and developmental activities such as training and involvement, as it empowers them to convey top notch administration to clients.

Employees' empowerment is the process of sharing power with employees, thereby enhancing their confidence in their ability to perform their jobs, and their belief that they are influential contributors to the organization. It has been observed that imparting power to employees enhances their feeling of self-efficiency and a sense of 'owning' a job. Empowered employees exude increased confidence while performing their jobs. It is the feeling of 'ownership and control' over their jobs which motivates employees to maximize their contribution in making the organization successful. In an age of increasing individualism, empowerment is what young job aspirants look for in organizations.

Many organizations follow team structures which have paved the way for empowerment of employees. Empowerment would be all the more necessary to speed up the process of decision-making, make use of environmental opportunities and to serve the customers and society better.

The purpose of empowerment is to free the employees from rigorous control and give them freedom to take responsibility for their own ideas and actions, to release hidden talents which would otherwise remain inaccessible. Empowerment offers a way of treating people with respect and dignity. It is a must for organizations that want to be successful in the competitive world.

Kumar & Kumar (2017) state that empowerment is been defined in numerous ways, but most authors agree that the core element of empowerment involves giving employees a discretion (or latitude) over certain task related activities.

Ollikainen, & Varis (2006) in Khadra & hacini (2018) state that empowering people is also seen as giving them authority and responsibility to make decisions affecting their work. They take responsibility for their actions and work free from the petty bureaucratic hassles that diminish value and waste time.

In Amir & Amen (2014), employee empowerment does not mean that management abandon from its responsibility of performance or for leading the organization. Rather, in an employee empowered organization, management's responsibility comes to create and foster an environment in which it is apparent that employee input is desired and cultivated. The management must trust and communicate with employees. They further state that when employees are empowered, their confidence degree and self-reliance will increase. This extra confidence is a good thing because it creates job satisfaction and high levels of productivity. However, in some cases, confidence levels can be taken too far and end up crossing the line into arrogance. Arrogant employees are difficult to deal with, do not take direction well and can become insubordinate. Working in this type of work environment takes its toll on employees and they once again become dissatisfied with their job and productivity levels decrease.

a) Empowerment Approaches

Hosein, G., Shahram, G. & Reza, P. M (2013) state that the approaches of empowerment included Mechanical Approach and Organic approach. In mechanical approach, empowerment means delegating power from the top to bottom with clear boundaries and limits and also strict accountability which increases managerial control (Boula 1994). Empowerment based on this view is a process during which senior management has developed a clear vision, programs and specific tasks to achieve it in the organization. He provides the information and resources needed by the employees to perform their duties. This empowerment approach also means decision in a particular range (Abdollahi & Nave, 2006).

The Organic approach is of the view that it comes from bottom to up, and reduce control. Based on this approach, empowerment is defined in terms of personal beliefs. According to this view, capable individuals have common characteristics; and which reflects the experiences or beliefs of employees about their role in the organization. Hence, empowerment is not something which managers carry out to employees instead is mindset of employees about their role in the organization. However, organization management can provide a required platform for empowerment of employees. (Spritzer 1995)

b) Training and Performance of Employees

Training has been seen as one of the key functions of human resources management (HRM). It has since been recognized and attracted several researches by many academic authors and scholars in the field of management and beyond. According to Gordon

(1992) defines training as the planned and systematic modification of behavior through learning events, activities and programs which result in the participants achieving the levels of knowledge, skills, competencies and abilities to carry out their work effectively. In Zahid (2014) training is a key element for improved performance; it can increase the level of individual and organizational competency. It is agreed that training holds the key to unlock the potential growth and development opportunities in order to achieve a competitive edge. Dessler (2000) the primary role of training is to improve the employees' skill for current and future duties and responsibilities. Training helps them to change with aspects like technology and competition.

Training programs, according to Acton & Golden (2002) are of the opinion that it helps in making acquaintance of employees with more advance technology and attaining robust competencies and skills in order to handle the functions and basics of newly introduced technical equipment. Training has the distinct role in the achievement of an organizational goal by incorporating the interests of organization and the workforce (Stone, 2002). It is worthy to state that a lot of researchers have opined that the acceptance of the importance of training in recent years has been heavily influenced by the intensified nature of competition and the relative success of organizations where investment in employee development is considerably emphasized (Beardwell et al. 2004)

Recognizing the relationship between training and employees' performance, some researchers have rather made some positive findings. In relation to the above, Wright & Geroy (2001) state that employee competencies change through effective training programs, and that it not only improves the overall performance of the employees to effectively perform their current jobs but also enhances the knowledge, skills an attitude of the workers necessary for the future job, thus contributing to superior organizational performance. Again, other studies have also affirmed the importance of training on performance. Swart, Mann, Brown & Price (2005) elaborate on training as a means of dealing with skill deficits and performance gaps as a way of improving employee performance. They further state that bridging the performance gap refers to implementing a relevant training intervention for the sake of developing particular skills and abilities of the employees and enhancing employee performance.

Training has been an important tool in increasing organizational productivity. Zahid (2014) states that most of the researches which included Colombo & Stanca (2008), Sepulveda (2005) and Konings & Vanormelingen, (2009) have vividly showed that training is a key and vital instrument in successful realization of the firm's goals and objectives, which eventually result in a higher

performance and productivity of the organization. In similar development, Armstrong(2000) opines that trained employees often work better as teams because everyone is aware of the expectations and can achieve them together smoothly. In addition, employees who receive regular training are more likely to accept change and come up with new ideas.

c) Delegation of Authority and Employees Job Satisfaction.

Ibrahim, Mayende & Muhamadi (2014) citing Yukl & Fu (1999) define delegation as a process that involves assigning important tasks to subordinates, giving subordinates responsibility for decisions formally made by the manager, and increasing the amount of work-related discretion allowed to subordinates, including the authority to make decisions without seeking prior approval from the manager (Yukl & Fu, 1999). Job satisfaction has been described as an individual's general attitude toward his or her job.

According to Price (1997) job satisfaction is the degree to which employees have a positive affective orientation towards employment. Job satisfaction has been conceptualized to involve the dimensions of rewards, promotions, rewards, promotions, work conditions and co-workers (Spector, 2008). It is unarguable that many researchers have seen delegation as an approach that enhances job satisfaction. Based on this, delegation of authority helps to overcome distance related obstacles to corporate-decision making through subjective intelligence and permits employees to be satisfied on their jobs. Muindi (2011) sees delegation as an important component and predictor of job satisfaction. Hence, many organizations in a bid to facilitate attainment of job satisfaction by employees, are applying the concept of delegation as an approach for realizing worker's job satisfaction which in turn lead to enhanced service delivery, higher productivity and reduced labor turn over.

d) Work Environment and Employee Commitment

Kohun (1992) defines working environment as an entirety which comprises the totality of forces, actions and other influential factors that are currently and, or potentially contending with the employee's activities and performance. Working environment is the sum of the interrelationship that exists within the employees and the environment in which the employees work. According to Beiz (2001) in Ushie, Agba, & Okorie (2015) work environment involves the physical, geographical locations as well as the immediate surroundings of the work place. Typically, it involves other factors relating to the place of employment such as security, additional perks and benefits of employment.

Opperman (2002) working environment is a composite of three major sub-environments: the technical environment, the human environment and

the organizational environment. Technical environment refers to tools, equipment, technological infrastructure and other physical or technical elements. The technical environment creates elements that enable employees perform their respective responsibilities and activities. The human environment refers to peers, others with whom employees relates, team and work groups, interactional issues, the leadership and management. This environment is designed in such a way that encourages informal interaction in the work place so that the opportunity to share knowledge and exchange ideas could be enhanced. This is a basis to attain maximum productivity. Organizational environment include systems, procedures, practices, values and philosophies. Management has control over organizational environment. Measurement system where people are rewarded on quantity, hence workers will have little interest in helping those workers who are trying to improve quality. Thus, issues of organizational environment influence employee's productivity.

Robbin & Judge (2011) in Mayowa & Folashade (2016) see organizational commitment is the degree to which employee identifies with a particular organization and its goals and wishing to maintain membership in the organization while Pareek (2004) defined it as person's feeling with regard to continuing his or her association with the organization, acceptance of the values and goals of the organization, and willingness to help the organization achieve such goals and values.

Akintayo (2010) noted that one of the reasons why commitment has attracted research attention is that organizations depend on committed employees to create and maintain competitive advantage and achieve superior performance. Various literatures have analyzed the relationship between work environment and organizational commitment.

Moos (1994) observed that involvement, co-worker cohesion, supervisory support, autonomy, task orientation, work pressure, clarity, managerial control, innovation and physical comfort, all are significant positive predictors of affective commitment which is one of the indicators of organizational commitment (Mayowa & Folashade, 2016).

B. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

a) Kanter's Structural Empowerment Theory (1993)

Kanter's theory of structural empowerment focuses on the structures within the organization rather than the individual's own qualities (Bradbury-Jones, Sambrook, & Irvine, 2007). Kanter believes that a leader's power will grow by sharing the power through empowering others and as a result, leaders will realize increased organizational performance (Fox, 1998). Furthermore, Kanter posits that with tools, information, and support, people's skill base

will improve, they will increasingly make informed decisions and overall accomplish more, thereby benefiting the organization as a whole (Fox, 1998).

According to Kanter, two systemic sources of power exist in organizations, these being formal and informal power. Formal power is that which accompanies high visibility jobs and requires a primary focus on independent decision making. Informal power comes from building relationships and alliances with peers and colleagues (Wagner et al., 2010). The six conditions required for empowerment to take place according to Kanter include:

- Opportunity for advancement
- Access to information
- Access to support
- Access to resources
- Formal Power
- Informal Power

These six conditions are what many organizational behaviorists have based their work and studies on. The basis of structural empowerment and psychological empowerment is derived from Kanter's work in the 1970's. They are identified as distinct sources of organizational power (Wagner et al., 2010)

By providing these conditions to employees, it has been found that there is increased job satisfaction, commitment, trust and a marked decrease in job burnout. Kanter's theory has proven to have measurable impact on employees' empowerment and job satisfaction as well as organizational morale and success, especially in healthcare settings (Wagner et al., 2010). It has also been noted that retention rates of healthcare professionals improve when empowerment principles such as decreased work pressure, greater peer cohesion, support from supervisors, and staff autonomy are put in place (Krebs, Madigan, & Tullai-McGuinness, 2008).

Through the evolution of healthcare in the past two decades there have been many challenges. These challenges have forced organizations and leaders to rethink their strategies of operations and structure. Kanter's theory still resonates as one of the most basic frameworks to guide practice in order to improve organizational efficacy. Where healthcare leaders have been able to put into practice empowerment models i.e Magnet Hospitals, there has been success within challenging times (Krebs et al., 2008). What follows is a review of application and comparison to Kanter's theory for healthcare settings in times of change. For many, it is a welcome paradigm shift for a desired and improved healthcare work setting.

IV. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Abdulkadir (2016) carried out a study aimed at determining the impact of employee empowerment and organizational performance. The researchers utilized convenient sampling to collect 70 questionnaires from three Telecommunication Firms in Mogadishu, Somalia. Employees of these were provided a questionnaire. Using correlation coefficient, the study found that organizational performance (Dependent variable) had significant positive influence with three independent variables namely: power, knowledge and information sharing. Also, the result of regression analysis found that three constructs had statistically significant, positive, and straight effects on organizational performance.

Sambil, Sihle & Charles (2018) conducted a research aimed at determining the level of employee empowerment and the impact it has on employee satisfaction in a manufacturing setup. A mixed methods research design was followed. Data was collected through structured questionnaires and then qualitative data through semi-structured interviews with 11 managers at the flavors division. The study results showed a significant level of employee empowerment.

William & Holmes (2021) carried out a research aimed at exploring how dimensions of employee empowerment increase organizational commitment and, in turn, reduce turnover intention; leading to a more sustained workforce. Drawing on the results of 346 surveys within the Canadian lodging industry, structural equation modeling was undertaken to examine the influence of empowerment on organizational commitment and organizational commitments influence on turnover intention. Findings suggest that employee empowerment, particularly when the ideals and standards between workers and their organization are aligned, creates a strong emotional commitment which appears to strongly reduce an employee's intention to leave.

Richa, Surat, & Amrinder (2016) conducted a research aimed at is to explore the different dimensions of employee empowerment and to determine the impact of employee empowerment tools on performance of private sector employees in Punjab. Structured questionnaire is used to collect the required primary data from 80 respondents in private sector in Punjab. Descriptive statistics, correlation, regression analysis, factor analysis and t-test are used as statistical tools in analysis. The study found that Performances of employees are significantly affected by independent decision making and open communication in the organization.

V. METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive research and a survey design was adopted. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources. The population of the study is 270 of both academic and non academic staff selected at random which is also the sample size of the study.

A. Description of the Research Instrument.

For the study, questionnaire was used as the research instrument, The questionnaire was designed using the Five point Likert scale that ranges from Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

B. Method of Data Analysis.

C. The data collected from the respondents were tabulated and analyzed using descriptive statistics of table of percentage, mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using

pearson product moment correlation and regression analysis model aided by SPSS v21.

D. Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient

$$r = \frac{n(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{(n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2)(n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2)}}$$

Degree of Freedom (df) = n-2

E. Regression model

$$\text{Org.Perf} = b_0 + b_1\text{EmpTra} + b_2\text{Del} + b_3\text{Wk.Env} + e$$

Org. Perf (dependent variable) = Organizational performance

b_0 = is the intercept

$b_1 \dots b_3$ = The regression coefficients

EmpTra = Employee training

Wk.Env = Working Environment

e = Standard error.

VI. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

S/N	No. Administered		Percent of No. administered/ No. returned	
	No. Administered	No. Returned	Percent of No. Administered	Percent of No. Returned
1	270	190	100%	70.4%

Table 1: Administration of Questionnaire

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The table shows that out of the 270 questionnaire i.e 100% distributed only 190 i.e 70.4% were returned.

S/N	QUESTION ITEM	RESPONSES					Descriptive Statistics		
		SA 5	A4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1	N	X—	SD
	Work Environment								
1	The general workplace design helps in performing my duty.	121	53	11	2	3	190	4.640	0.524
2	Adequate safety measures at workplace enhance morale of employees.	156	26	8	0	0	190	4,100	0.530
3	Incentive is required for optimum performance	168	22	0	0	0	190	4.910	0.294
4	Support from ones superior enhances performance.	90	85	14	1	0	190	4.630	0.515
	Employee Commitment								
5	I love my job	103	71	8	5	3	190	4.480	0.672
6	I am satisfied with my work in the organization	116	56	18	0	0	190	4.180	0.948
7	I am identified with the organization goals.	78	89	9	4	10	190	4.310	0.526
8	I have stake in the future of the organization	75	56	49	1	9	190	3.990	0.752

Table 2: Questionnaire analysis on employee training and performance

Field Survey, 2022

The table above shows that training received by the employees affects the morale of the employees, reduces error and accident rate and also enhances customers’ satisfaction through loyalty and patronage.

S/N	QUESTION ITEM	RESPONSES					Descriptive Statistics		
		SA 5	A 4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	SD
	Employee Training								
1	The training you have received has influenced your attitude and behaviour.	89	99	2	0	0	190	4.46	.520
2	I am satisfied with the training method that was applied	94	90	6	0	0	190	4.46	.560
3	I have learned more skills and acquired additional knowledge than before	96	94	0	0	0	190	4.51	.501
	Employee Performance								
4	My morale is boosted since trained	1	182	4	2	1	190	3.95	.337
5	The rate of errors and accident in the organization has been reduced	42	126	15	7	0	190	4.07	.667
6	Low rate of absenteeism in the institution	0	131	26	1	32	190	3.35	1.120

Table 3: Responses on delegation of authority and job satisfaction Field Survey, 2022

The table above has revealed that delegation of authority that involves making decisions independently, having the trust and confidence of the superior have alignment with the employees' happiness, attachment to his job superior's recognition of his input.

S/N	QUESTION ITEM	RESPONSES					Descriptive Statistics		
		SA 5	A 4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	SD
	Delegation of Authority								
1	I have handled a project or made decisions independently in the institution	106	72	0	9	3	190	4.43	0.850
2	I have the trust and confidence my superior to make decisions at times	75	106	6	0	3	190	4.31	0.691
3	I have the authority to act on behalf of my superior in his absence	106	77	0	7	0	190	4.46	0.702
	JOB SATISFACTION								
7	I am happy with my present job responsibilities	95	90	0	5	0	190	4.45	0.638
8	I have attachment towards the work I perform	81	86	3	6	4	190	4.45	0.663
9	I feel my superior recognizes my input with respect	98	86	0	6	0	190	3.35	1.120

Table 4: Responses on work environment and employee commitment

Field Survey, 2022

From the above table work environment which involves the general work place design, safety measures, incentives and the superior-subordinate relationship affect the employees love for his job, satisfaction and identification with the organization.

Test of Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Training does not have any effect on employees’ job performance*

		Employee_Training	Job_Performance
Employee_Training	Pearson Correlation	1	0.988*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010
	N	3	3
Job_Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.988*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	
	N	3	3

Table 5:Correlations

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		
					R Square Change	F Change	df1
1	.988 ^a	.976	.952	.08485	.976	40.333	1

Table 6: Model Summary^b

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee_Training

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.290	1	.290	40.333	.010 ^b
	Residual	.007	1	.007		
	Total	.298	2			

Table 7: ANOVA^a

a. Dependent Variable: Job_Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee_Training

Source: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v.23

Test of Hypothesis 2

H₀₂:Delegation of authority does not encourage employee job satisfactions

		Delegation	Job_satisfaction
Delegation	Pearson Correlation	1	0.655
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.011
	N	3	3
Job_satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.655	1
	Sig (1 tailed)	0.011	
	N		3

Table 8: Correlations

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.655 ^a	.429	0.143	.08485

Table 9: Model Summary
a. Predictors: (Constant), Delegation

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	.005	1	.005	.750	.011 ^b
1 Residual	.007	1	.007		
Total	.013	2			

Table 10:ANOVA^a

- a. Dependent Variable: Job_satisfaction
- b. Predictors: (constant), Delegation

Source: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v.23

Test of Hypothesis 3

What is the effect of work environment on employees' commitment?

		Work environment	Employee commitment
Work environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.755
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.002
	N	4	4
Employee commitment	Pearson Correlation	.755	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.002	
	N	4	4

Table 11: Correlations

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.255 ^a	.065	-.402	.24516

Table 12: Model Summary

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work environment

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.008	1	.008	.140	.002 ^b
	Residual	.120	2	.060		
	Total	.129	3			

Table 13: ANOVA^a

a. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work environment

Source: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v.23

VII. INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

From the test of hypothesis 1, the Pearson correlation value of 0.98 shows that the relationship between employee training and job performance is positive. Hence employee training counts for about 98% variations in the job performance of the employees. The strength of the relationship is strong since the value is greater than 0.3. Since the significant 2-tailed P-value is 0.010 which is less than the P value of 0.05 (significant value by default) accept the Alternate hypothesis (H_i) which states that there is significant relationship between employee training and job performance.

From the test of hypothesis 2, the Pearson correlation value of 0.65 shows that the relationship between delegation of authority and job satisfaction is positive. About 65% variations of delegation is explained in the job satisfaction. The strength of the relationship is strong since the value 0.65 is greater than 0.3. The significant 2-tailed P-value is 0.011 which is less than the P value of 0.05 (significant value by default) accept the Alternate hypothesis (H_i) which states that delegation of authority affect employee's job satisfaction.

From the test of hypothesis 3, the Pearson correlation value of 0.755 shows that the relationship between work environment and employees' commitment is positive. About 75% variations of work environment is explained in the employee commitment. The strength of the relationship is strong since the value 0.65 is greater than 0.3. The significant 2-tailed P-value is 0.002 which is less than the P value of 0.05 (significant value by default) accept the

Alternate hypothesis (H_i) which states that work environment effects employees' commitment.

VIII. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS/CONCLUSION

Employees are the core elements of every organization, and for them to strive to achieve the organizational goals there is need to recognize them. Their impact on organization performance is significant as their roles boost the firms' competitiveness, image and also enhance customer loyalty. When employees have the tools and resources to successfully manage or lead their goals and drive their own career the benefits are enormous. Empowerment through training, delegation of authority and good work environment increases the employees' job performance, satisfaction and commitment in the organization. I will also make them go the extra mile, follow the best practices, have good communication, embrace change and gives them the opportunity to boost the image of the organization before its publics.

Apart from the aforementioned empowerment strategies, though not covered in the research work, it is also observed that the organization also sponsors the employees in the areas of seminars, workshop, and conferences both internationally and locally, use of financial incentives, recognition of the employees' hard work through various awards and a host of them.

Moreover, other factors that could increase the performance of employees that management should also

take into consideration included the pay or salary, good working conditions, promotion, fringe benefits, bonus, and effective human resources policies. These to a large extent determine the level of job satisfaction of the employees, commitment and productivity.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

- The institution should ensure that the work environment is conducive for employees to perform. In other words, workplace design, provision of safety measures, workplace incentive, supportive superior relationship and comfortable working hours are necessary to boost employees' productivity.
- Most employees are motivated by the external factors such as the pay or salary, good working conditions, regular promotion, fringe benefits, bonus, commission and profit sharing. Hence, the institution should make provision for these factors to encourage employees' creativity, productivity and achieve organizational goals.
- Good superior-subordinate relationship is a tool that empowers employees psychologically. It brings the best from them and could reduce high rate of absenteeism and employee turnover. Hence good and productive interpersonal relationship should be encouraged among the members of the organization.
- Training of employees should be imbibed and treated as culture; and also seen as a tool that will strengthen the competitive position of the organization.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abdollahi, B & Nave, E. (2006). Employees Empowerment, Golden Key of Management. Publication Virayesh. Tehran
- [2.] Abdulkadir, M (2016). Employee Empowerment and Organizational Performance: Empirical Study from Telecommunication Companies in Mogadishu-Somalia. IJRSS Volume 6, Issue 7 ISSN: 2249-2496
- [3.] Alejandro, O. R. & Yolanda, B.A. (2014). Empowering Employees: Structural Empowerment as Antecedent of Job Satisfaction in University Settings. Psychological Thought. psyc.psychopen.eu | 2193-7281
- [4.] Amir, A & Amen, I. (2014). The Impact of Employee Empowerment on Job Satisfaction: Theoretical Study. American Journal of Research Communication, 2014, 2(1): 13-26} www.usa-journals.com, ISSN: 2325-4076
- [5.] Boula, H (1994). Process of Developments and Adult Education Issues in The World. Journal Talim & Tarbiat. eleventh years. No. 1
- [6.] Gordon, B. (1992). Are Canadian Firms Under Investing in Training? Canadian Business Economics 1,1, 25–33
- [7.] Hosein, G., Shahram, G. & Reza, P. M (2013). Overview of Employees Empowerment in Organizations. Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter) Vol. 3, No.2; Sep. 2013
- [8.] Ibrahim, A. M; Mayende, S. T. & Muhamadi, L. (2014). Delegation and Job Satisfaction: An Evaluation of the Relationship within Uganda's Primary Education Sector. Global Journal of HUMAN-SOCIAL SCIENCE Linguistics & Education Volume 14 Issue 1 Version 1.0 Year 2014
- [9.] Kohun, S. (1992). Business environment. Ibadan: University Press
- [10.] Kumar J & Kumar, A (2017). Employee Empowerment – An Empirical Study. Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management Volume 17 Issue 4 Version 1.0 Year 2017
- [11.] Mayowa, O & Folashade, A. (2016) Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology, 9 (1) (2016)
- [12.] Ollikainen, M., & Varis, J. (2006). Human Errors Play a Remarkable Role in Sheet Metal Industry. *Mechanika*, 5 (61), 51-56
- [13.] Rajesh R (2015). Role of Employee Empowerment in Organizational Performance. International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field ISSN – 2455-0620 Volume - 2, Issue - 4, Apr – 2015
- [14.] Richa, M., Surat. S., & Amrinder, S. (2016). Employees Empowerment and their Performance in Private Sector: An Analytical Study. Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management Volume 16 Issue 12 Version 1.0 Year 2016
- [15.] Sambil, C. M, Sihle, M. & Charles, M. (2018). The impact of employee empowerment on organizational performance in a flavors and fragrance manufacturing company in South Africa. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326977251>
- [16.] Spector, P. (2008). Industrial and Organisational Behaviour (5th edition). (5th Edition ed.). New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- [17.] Spritzer, Gretchen M. (1995). Psychological Empowerment in Work Place, Dimensions, Measurement.
- [18.] Swart, J., Mann, C., Brown, S. & Price, A. (2005). Human Resource Development: Strategy and Tactics. Oxford. Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann Publications
- [19.] Ushie, E. M., Agba, A. M. Ogaboh & Chimaobi O. (2015). Work Environment and Employees' Commitment in Agro-Based Industries in Cross River State, Nigeria. Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Sociology & Culture Volume 15 Issue 6 Version 1.0 Year 2015.
- [20.] Wright, P. & Geroy, D. G. (2001). Changing the Mindset: The Training Myth and The Need for Word-Class performance. International Journal of Human Resource Management 12,4, 586–600.
- [21.] Zahid, H. B. (2014). Impact of Training on Employee Performance: A Study of Retail Banking Sector in India. HRM Volume: 3 | Issue: 6 | June 2013 | ISSN - 2249-555X
- [22.] <https://structuralempowerment.weebly.com/kanters-theory.htm>